

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MWANGI****FIRST NAME: AGBES****PROGRAM CODE : LLM****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: P1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

INTRODUCTION TO ACADEMIC AND PROFESSIONAL WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

My training as an advocate has conditioned my mind to pick out the dos and do nots of any set up and in the context of my new life as a student at EUCLID I have been able to pick up certain rules on academic and professional writing which I intend to highlight in this paper. As I was going through the provided course pack material, I could not help but notice that some of the rules such as “no plagiarism” are so critical that their breach would attract stiff penalties such as failed grades. Other rules though prohibitive in nature however, do not seem to attract any penalties, these are rules on consistency in the writing style and in particular on use of punctuations and quotation marks, abbreviations, acronyms, spelling system, contractions amongst others.

2) ACADEMIC WRITING RULES

Being a legal practitioner, I should be forgiven for imagining that offences are creatures of statutes only. In my journey as an academic writer *par excellence* I will need to broaden my mind to the possibilities of there being other offences not defined by statutes like plagiarism (EUCLID 2015, 12). The offence of plagiarism can occur in two ways, first when one uses words from a source without quotation marks or when one uses a close paraphrase from a source and secondly when one takes ideas from a source without citing it (EUCLID 2015, 44). To avoid committing this academic offence I will have to constantly remind myself to cite the source of all information acquired from other people’s work with

the exception of information considered common knowledge that can be found in numerous areas (EUCLID 2015, 30).

The use of citations is important in judgment writing as it is in academic writing. This is because as a trial magistrate I rely so much on cited cases in making decisions to justify my findings hence I have to clearly state the source of the law so that the parties in the case can verify it and satisfy themselves that the decision is legally sound. There are two main approaches to citing work, the use of in-text citations, and list of works cited (EUCLID 2015, 15). In-text citation “refers to citing the piece of work you are using within the actual text itself” whereas list of works cited refers to “the ‘bibliography’ or the ‘references’ listed at the end of the book” (EUCLID 2015, 16 & 33). I realize that as a budding academic writer I will need to be conscious on the use of too many quotations since my work will end up looking like it is not my own (EUCLID 2015, 22). This is in great contrast with my experience in judgment writing where I use a lot of quotations from cases by the higher courts to justify my decisions and this is encouraged through the doctrine of judicial precedent. I am however dismayed to learn that I have been a serial offender for using long quotations with quotation marks in my judgments yet the proper way is to use separate indented paragraphs without the quotation marks (EUCLID 2015, 20).

Another area that requires consistency is the use of punctuation marks with quotation marks. There are two major variations, the American English style which requires that punctuation marks are always inside the closing quotation marks and the British English style in which the punctuation marks are placed after the closing quotation marks. In my experience as a writer I find that I am more inclined to the American English style and I attribute this to the dominance of American culture on language in my country. The two English systems are however said to be “more similar than different,” and it can get really overwhelming trying to master all the style differences such as the spelling, the pronunciations, the date format, and the abbreviations as set out in the course pack on pages 54-60 (EUCLID 2015, 54). Thankfully, Microsoft word’s software makes it easy for the writer to ensure consistency in use of the language’s rules of style with its valuable formatting tools such as the review language tab.

Other useful tools that assist writers with consistency in their writing are style guides. At EUCLID, Master of Laws (LLM) students are expected to use the Turabian or blue book rule of style. I am personally not familiar with the blue book style and will be at ease using the Turabian rule of style which is also known as the Chicago Style (EUCLID 2015, 66). Where in doubt on the proper spelling, use of abbreviations, capitalization of words, compound words, and other writing style elements the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) crib sheet on page 66 of the course pack provides a comprehensive guide. A student however need not weigh down their mind with these details as use of virtual research assistants such as “Zotero” will come in handy to ensure full compliance.

Besides ensuring consistency in the writing style a writer should ensure they deliver their message to the reader in simple and easy to understand language. Legal practitioners, myself included are fond of using legalese perhaps for effect or to sound more learned. This is not acceptable in academic writing because its use may end up confusing the reader

and not passing the intended message. It was however a delight for me to see words such as *ab initio*, *bona fide*, *caveat emptor*, *defacto*, *dejure* amongst other common Latin words used in court and their English translation as part of the course material (EUCLID 2015, 81). I however undertake to steer clear of these words and instead use plain English because I am committed to complying with all the rules of academic writing.

The proper use of grammar is also critical in academic writing therefore, to be successful in academic writing I need to reacquaint myself with the proper use of commas especially when joining two independent clauses, to bracket nonrestrictive phrases which are not integral to the meaning of the sentence, and when starting a sentence with an introductory phrase (EUCLID 2015, 46). Other grammatical aspects that I will be required to recall and mostly re learn are the proper use of verbs, nouns, adjectives, possessive terms and how to write numbers amongst other requirements. A novice like me however, need not worry so much about breaking grammar rules as writing aids such as Grammarly, which I have learnt about from the orientation material, will assist them in securing full grammatical compliance.

3) CONCLUSION

Having gone through the introductory material on academic and professional writing I feel that it can be such a daunting exercise especially because of the many rules that need to be complied with as opposed to judgment writing which basically requires the setting out of facts, the application of the law on the facts, the decision and the reasons for the decision. Although judgment writing is part of professional writing the main concern in judgement writing is to set out these four elements in simple English without much concern on the style being used. As a student of academic writing I will need to pay more attention to the rules discussed above, but my greatest consolation is that with aids such as Zotero, Grammarly and the style manuals the journey will be enjoyable and worthwhile

REFERENCES

Euclid University. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. Retrieved from: <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401-period-1/> (accessed On December 12, 2019)

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.